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MECHANISM OF FORMATION AND ENERGY TRANSFER IN MAGNETIC ROCKS OF KARACHAY-CHERKESSIA (NORTH CAUCASUS)

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Abstract

The mechanism of formation and energy transfer in rocks as crystals with impurity systems of donor and acceptor atoms is considered. An assessment was made of the times and concentrations at which the transfer process is not affected by the disorder of the acceptor environment and the decay is exponential. The question of the influence of excitation diffusion across donors on the rate of the process is also considered. A kinetic equation has been obtained that describes the evolution of the population of donor states averaged over impurity configurations in the presence of donor-donor interaction. This equation shows that the deactivation of donors accelerates and can take on an exponential character.

It has been shown that the diffusion process in a disordered system proceeds more slowly than in an ordered one. Moreover, the diffusion of excitation through a disordered donor system determines the type of quenching.

An equation for energy transfer in magnetic rocks (crystals) was obtained and a condition corresponding to diffusion was found. An assessment was made of the times and concentrations at which the transfer process is not affected by the disorder of the acceptor environment and the decay is exponential. It is shown that the diffusion process in a disordered system proceeds more slowly than in an ordered one, and the diffusion of excitation through a disordered donor system determines its type. In the formation of energy transfer between impurities in magnetic crystals, the main role is played by the disorder of their arrangement along lattice sites. The transport equation in an ordered medium and the conditions of diffusion at the initial moment of the process are derived. It was found that in a disordered system of particles (rocks) connected to each other by short-range interactions, the main role is played by the disorder of their arrangement along lattice sites, and the law can only manifest itself in the absence of migration of donor excitations.

Keywords: Atomic magnetic order, lattice, crystal, energy, magnetic rocks, energy transfer.

Introduction

Atomic magnetic order in magnetic materials arises as a result of the ordered arrangement of atoms in the crystal lattices. The nature of this ordering is quantum mechanical, the energy due to which it occurs is exchangeable.

In magnetic minerals, crystallographic anisotropy arises due to orbital magnetic dipole interaction. Therefore, in the formation of energy transfer in magnetic

minerals, the main role is played by the disordered arrangement of impurities at lattice sites and energy transfer in magnetic ores remains relevant.

The purpose of this work is to consider the mechanism of formation and energy transfer in magnetic rock ores, Karachay-Cherkessia (North Caucasus).

Practical part

To achieve this goal, we considered the kinetic equation in matrix form:

$$\frac{\partial n}{\partial t} = \hat{K}n - \frac{n}{\tau_D}, \quad (1)$$

where $n_{\mathbf{r}} = n(\mathbf{r}, t) p_D(\mathbf{r})$, $n(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is the probability of excitation on a donor located at node $\mathbf{r}$ ($p_D(\mathbf{r}) = 1$, if there is a donor at point $\mathbf{r}$, otherwise $p_D(\mathbf{r}) = 0$) τ_D is the intrinsic lifetime of the donor state, the matrix elements $\hat{K}$ are equal to:

$$\begin{aligned} K_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'} = & p_D(\mathbf{r}) W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') p_D(\mathbf{r}') - \delta_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'} p_D(\mathbf{r}) \sum_{\mathbf{r}''} W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'') p_D(\mathbf{r}'') - \\ & - \delta_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'} p_D(\mathbf{r}) \sum_{\mathbf{r}''} W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'') p_A(\mathbf{r}''); \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$W_{ik}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ is the probability of transfer per unit time of excitation from an atom of type i at point $\mathbf{r}$ to an atom of type k at point $\mathbf{r}'$, $p_A(\mathbf{r}) = 1(0)$, if at point $\mathbf{r}$ the acceptor is located (absent). Solving (1), we get

$$n(t) = \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_D}\right) \exp(\hat{K}t)n(0).$$

The donor excitation probability averaged over impurity configurations $N(\mathbf{r}, t) = \overline{n(\mathbf{r}, t) p_D(\mathbf{r})}$ is thus equal to

$$N(\mathbf{r}, t) = \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_D}\right) \sum_{\mathbf{r}'} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^n}{n!} \overline{(\hat{K})_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'} p_D(\mathbf{r}') n(\mathbf{r}', 0)}. \tag{3}$$

Using the pulse method, we can assume that

$$N(\mathbf{r}, 0) = n(\mathbf{r}, 0) \overline{p_D(\mathbf{r})}. \tag{4}$$

In the static case, in the n th term of the power series in (3) the sum arises:

$$(-t)^n \sum_{\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_n} W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_1) \dots W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_n) \times \overline{p_A(\mathbf{r}_1) \dots p_A(\mathbf{r}_n)}, \tag{5}$$

Averaging expressions (5) we obtain a model of a homogeneous chaotic $\overline{p_D(\mathbf{r})} = c_D, \overline{p_A(\mathbf{r})} = c_A, c_D, c_A$ direction-independent r.

Then, the average $\overline{p_A(\mathbf{r}_1) \dots p_A(\mathbf{r}_n)}$ is equal to $(b_1^A)^{l_1} \dots (b_k^A)^{l_k} \dots, \sum_k k l_k = n$, the meaning of the indices k, l_k is explained in the caption to the figure; the factor b_k^A generated by the vertex at which k lines converge is equal to:

$$b_k^A = \frac{d^k}{d\xi^k} \ln(1 + e^\xi) \Big|_{\xi = \ln\left(\frac{c_A}{1-c_A}\right)} (k \geq 1), \tag{6}$$

Based on expression (5) we have:

$$n! \sum_{l_1, \dots} \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{l_k!} \left[\sum_{\mathbf{r}'} (-t)^k \frac{W_{DA}^k(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') b_k^A}{k!} \right]^{l_k} \Big|_{\left(\sum_k k l_k = n\right)}. \tag{7}$$

We substitute formula (7) into (3) and change the order of summation

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{l_1, \dots} \Big|_{\left(\sum_k k l_k = n\right)} \rightarrow \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{l_1, \dots} \Big|_{\left(\sum_k l_k = m\right)}$$

Reversing the row gives:

$$\begin{aligned} N(\mathbf{r}, t) &= N(\mathbf{r}, 0) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m!} \sum_{l_1, \dots} m! \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[\sum_{\mathbf{r}'} \frac{(-t)^k W_{DA}^k(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') b_k^A}{k!} \right]^{l_k} \frac{1}{l_k!} = \\ &= N(\mathbf{r}, 0) \exp \sum_{\mathbf{r}'} \left\{ -\ln(1 + e^\xi) + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-t)^k W_{DA}^k(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')}{k!} \frac{d^k}{d\xi^k} \ln(1 + e^\xi) \right\} \Big|_{\xi = \ln\left(\frac{c_A}{1-c_A}\right)} = \\ &= N(\mathbf{r}, 0) \exp \sum_{\mathbf{r}'} \left\{ -\ln(1 + e^\xi) + \ln[1 + \exp(\xi - t W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'))] \right\} \Big|_{\xi = \ln\left(\frac{c_A}{1-c_A}\right)} = \\ &= N(\mathbf{r}, 0) \exp \sum_{\mathbf{r}'} \ln[1 - c_A + c_A e^{-t W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')}] \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Integrating over $\mathbf{r}'$ we get:

$$\Delta W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') \square W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'), \tag{9}$$

where $\Delta W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}' + \mathbf{a}) - W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$, $\mathbf{a}$ is the vector of elementary translation of the lattice. For $t > t_m$, it follows from formula (8) that:

$$\begin{aligned}
N(\mathbf{r}, t) &= N(\mathbf{r}, 0) \exp \left\{ \frac{2\pi}{3} \frac{r_0^3}{\Omega} \sqrt{\frac{t}{\tau_D}} \int_0^\infty \frac{d\zeta}{\zeta^{3/2}} \ln(1 - c_A + c_A e^{-\zeta}) \right\} = \\
&= N(\mathbf{r}, 0) \exp \left\{ -\frac{4\pi^{3/2}}{3} \frac{r_0^3}{\Omega} \sqrt{\frac{t}{\tau_D}} (c_A + \beta c_A^2 + \gamma c_A^3 + \dots) \right\};
\end{aligned} \tag{eleven}$$

where $\beta \approx 0.29$, $\gamma \approx 0.1$, Ω is the volume of the unit cell of the lattice.

Considering the problem $W_{DA} = 0$ in the Laplace representation, we have:

$$N(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\mathbf{r}'} p_D(\mathbf{r}') \left(\frac{\hat{K}^n}{p^n} \right)_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'} \frac{N(\mathbf{r}', 0)}{p c_D}. \tag{12}$$

Then, for $N(t)$ it turns out:

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial t} = \hat{\phi}(0) N(t) + \int_0^t \frac{\partial \hat{\phi}(\tau)}{\partial \tau} N(t - \tau) d\tau. \tag{13}$$

The solution $N(\mathbf{r}, t) = \text{const}$, satisfying the original equation (1), follows from the property $\hat{\phi}(\tau)$:

$$\sum_{\mathbf{r}'} \varphi_{\mathbf{r}'}(t) = 0, \tag{14}$$

Substituting (14) into (12), we find

$$\varphi_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'}(0) = c_D \left[W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') - \delta_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'} \sum_{\mathbf{r}''} W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'') \right]. \tag{15}$$

If we discard the integral term in (13), then the remaining equation will exactly coincide with the transport equation in an ordered medium, which can be reduced under appropriate conditions to the diffusion equation. This possibility, however, is available only at the initial moments of the process. Over time, a correction appears that takes into account the chaotic distribution of donors over the crystal and is represented by the integral term in (13).

Let us calculate $\hat{\phi}(t)$ in a linear approximation:

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
\hat{\phi}(t) &= \hat{\phi}^{(1)}(t) + O(c_D^2); \\
\varphi_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'}^{(1)}(t) &= -\delta_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'} c_D \sum_{\mathbf{r}''} W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'') \exp[-2W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'')t] + \\
&+ c_D W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') \exp[-2W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')t].
\end{aligned} \right\} \tag{16}$$

Making small transformations we have:

$$\int_0^t \frac{\partial \hat{\phi}(\tau)}{\partial \tau} N(t - \tau) d\tau \approx \left[\int_0^t \frac{\partial \hat{\phi}(\tau)}{\partial \tau} d\tau \right] N(t). \tag{17}$$

Assuming that the scatter is homogeneous and passing to the Fourier representation, we have:

$$N_{\mathbf{k}} = \sum_{\mathbf{r}} N(\mathbf{r}) e^{i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{r}}, \quad W_{\mathbf{k}} = \sum_{\mathbf{r}} W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') e^{i\mathbf{k}(\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}')}. \tag{18}$$

Next, it's easy to get

$$N_{\mathbf{k}}(t) = N_{\mathbf{k}}(0) \exp \left[\int_0^t \varphi_{\mathbf{k}}(\tau) d\tau \right]. \tag{18}$$

Passing to the inverse $\mathbf{r}$ -representation, we obtain:

$$N(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{\Omega}{(2\pi)^3} \int d\mathbf{k} N_{\mathbf{k}}(0) \exp \left\{ -i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{r} + c_D \sum_{\mathbf{r}'} [e^{-2W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')t} - 1] \sin^2 \frac{\mathbf{k}(\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}')}{2} \right\}. \tag{19}$$

From formula (18) it follows that the diffusion process exists over a period of time $\sim \tau_s$:

$$\frac{\Omega}{(2\pi)^3} \int d\mathbf{k} N_{\mathbf{k}}(0) \exp \left\{ -i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{r} - c_D \sum_{|\mathbf{r}'| < R_m} \sin^2 \left(\frac{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{r}'}{2} \right) \right\}. \tag{20}$$

If the initial distribution is spherically symmetric, then

$$N(\mathbf{r}, 0) = N_0 \exp \left(-\frac{|\mathbf{r}|^2}{\sigma^2} \right), \quad (\sigma \ll R_m), \quad N_{\mathbf{k}}(0) = \frac{\pi^{3/2} N_0 \sigma^3}{\Omega} \exp \left(\frac{k^2 \sigma^2}{4} \right),$$

then we get that

$$N(\mathbf{r}, \infty) = N_0 \left(\frac{\sigma}{\Delta} \right)^3 \exp \left(-\frac{|\mathbf{r}|^2}{\Delta^2} \right),$$

$$\Delta^2 = \sigma^2 + c_D \sum_{|\mathbf{r}| < R_m} |\mathbf{r}|^2.$$

In a disordered system of particles connected to each other by short-range interactions, the diffusion mechanism does not lead to a relatively noticeable “resorption” of excitation throughout the crystal.

$$N(t) = N^{(1)}(t) + N^{(2)}(t) + \dots; \quad (21)$$

Next, replacing the sum with the integral over $\mathbf{r}'$ we have:

$$\sum_{\mathbf{r}'} [e^{-2W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')t} - 1] \sin^2 \frac{\mathbf{k}(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}')}{2} = \frac{2\pi}{\Omega k^3} J(x), \quad (22)$$

$$\text{Where } W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = 1 / \tau_D (r_1 / |\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|)^6$$

$$J(x) = \int_0^\infty dx x^2 \left(1 - \frac{\sin x}{x} \right) \left(e^{-\frac{x}{x^6}} - 1 \right), \quad x = \frac{2t}{\tau_D} r_1^6 k^6. \quad (23)$$

Considering the smallness in the region $-x J(x)$ we get:

$$J(x) \approx \frac{x^{5/6}}{6} \int_0^\infty dx x^4 \left(e^{-\frac{1}{x^6}} - 1 \right) (x \ll 1). \quad (24)$$

Substituting (22), (24) into (19), we find:

$$N^{(1)}(\mathbf{r}, t) \approx \frac{\Omega}{(2\pi)^3} \int d\mathbf{k} \exp\{-i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{r} - Ak^2\} N_{\mathbf{k}}(0), \quad (25)$$

Where

$$A = \frac{2^{5/6} \pi c_D r_1^5}{3\Omega} \left(\frac{t}{\tau_D} \right)^{5/6} \int_0^\infty dx x^4 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{1}{x^6}} \right).$$

For $x \ll 1$ we have:

$$\frac{\tau_D}{(r_1 k^*)^6} > 1 > \tau_D \left(\frac{|\mathbf{a}|}{r_1} \right)^6, \quad (26)$$

where k^* is the characteristic value of the wave vector for the initial distribution $N_{\mathbf{k}}(0)$.

The influence of excitation diffusion through a donor system on the process of resonant quenching in rock (crystal).

Let the arrangement of donors in the crystal be, for ordered ($c_D = 1$) and disordered ($c_D \ll 1$).

To do this, let us calculate the sum (13) and let the probability of quenching of different donors by the acceptors surrounding them not correlate with each other.

as with $c_D = 1$ the corresponding b_i^D wounds are zero.

Next, solving the Voltaire integral equation of the second kind

$$N(t) = N_{ct.}(t) e^{-\frac{t}{T}} + \int_0^t d\tau \hat{S}(t-\tau) e^{-\frac{\tau-t}{T}} N(\tau), \quad (27)$$

where $N_{ct.}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ - is the solution to the problem in the static case;

$$\frac{1}{T} = \sum_{\mathbf{r}'} W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'), \quad S(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}' | t) = W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') \frac{N_{ct.}(\mathbf{r}, t)}{N(\mathbf{r}, 0)}. \quad (28)$$

Then $N^*(t) = \sum_{\mathbf{r}} N(\mathbf{r}, t)$, expressed by the equation:

$$N^*(t) = N_{ct.}^*(t) e^{-\frac{t}{T}} + \frac{1}{N^*(0)T} \int_0^t d\tau N_{ct.}^*(t-\tau) e^{-\frac{\tau-t}{T}} N^*(\tau). \quad (29)$$

For $N_{ct.}^*(t) = N^*(0) e^{-\sqrt{\alpha t}}$ the equation we obtain a solution in the form:

$$N^*(t) = N^*(0) \frac{e^{-\frac{t}{T}}}{2\pi i} \int_{p_0-i\infty}^{p_0+i\infty} dp \frac{e^{\alpha p t} f(p)}{1 - \frac{f(p)}{\alpha T}}, \text{ (thirty)}$$

Where

$$f(p) = \frac{1}{p} - \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2p\sqrt{p}} e^{\frac{1}{4p}} \left[1 - \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{p}}\right) \right].$$

For the quantity $N^*(t)$ that determines the quantum yield of systems we have:

$$N_1^*(t) = N^*(0) \exp[S^{(1)}(t)], \quad (31)$$

Where

$$S^{(1)}(t) = \int_0^t \Phi_{k=0}^{(1)}(\tau) d\tau.$$

Summing (30) we find $S^{(1)}(t)$:

$$\begin{aligned} S^{(1)}(t) = & c_A \sum_{\mathbf{r}'} \{ \exp[-W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')t] - 1 \} \frac{c_A c_D}{2} \sum_{\mathbf{r}' \neq \mathbf{r}'' \neq \mathbf{r}} \{ -\exp[-W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'')t] - \\ & - \exp[-W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'')t] + \left[1 + \frac{2W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')}{\sqrt{B(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'')}} \right] \exp \left[\frac{\wp(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'')t}{2} + \frac{\sqrt{B(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'')t}}{2} - \right. \\ & \left. - W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'')t \right] + \left[1 - \frac{2W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')}{\sqrt{B(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'')}} \right] \exp \left[\frac{\wp(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'')t}{2} - \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{\sqrt{B(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'')t}}{2} - W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'')t \right] \}, \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} B(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'') &= [W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'') - W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')]^2 + 4W_{DD}^2(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'), \\ \wp(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'') &= W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'') - W_{DA}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') - 2W_{DD}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'). \end{aligned}$$

The first term (32) describes the process of quenching the donor state, the second term is due to the “mixing” effect of excitation diffusion through the donor system.

Conclusions:

1. An equation for energy transfer in crystals of magnetic ores has been obtained, which can be reduced under appropriate conditions to a diffusion equation.

2. It is shown that such a possibility, however, exists only at the initial moments of the process. And over time, a correction appears that takes into account the chaotic distribution of donors over the crystal and is represented by an integral term.

3. An assessment was made of the times and concentrations at which the transfer process is not affected by the disorder of the acceptor environment and the decay is exponential.

4. An equation has been derived for the deactivation of donors, which accelerates and takes on an exponential character.

5. It has been shown that the diffusion process in a disordered system proceeds more slowly than in an ordered one, and the diffusion of excitation through a disordered donor system determines its type.

6. In the formation of energy transfer between impurities in magnetic crystals, the main role is played by

the disorder of their arrangement along lattice sites.

5. It was found that in a disordered system of particles connected to each other by short-range interactions, the main role is played by the disorder of their arrangement along lattice sites. This law can only manifest itself in the absence of excitation migration through the donor system

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